

STRESS VARIATION IN HIGH STRENGTH FILM ADHESIVE BONDLINES FOR FLUSH SCARF BONDED JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

With the help of Finite Element calculations the governing stress distributions of flush scarf bonded joints have been visualized. The investigation shows the difference between the bondline stresses having either isotropic adherents or CFC laminates. Furthermore the study makes a brief discussion to comply with the manufacturing standard of repairs and concentrates on 3-dimensional calculations to demonstrate elasto-plastic effects of the examined high strength adhesive. A summary is given accounting for the principal results which shall give useful practical information for engineers in charge of composite repairs.

Key Words: CFC repair, bonded joint, stress calculation

1. PURPOSE AND GOAL OF INVESTIGATION

Within the next few years new aircraft will enter service whose outer surface have a very high percentage of carbon fibre composites (CFC), therefore the need for appropriate repair scenarios becomes evident. The method of scarf patch repair especially offers a variety of advantages compared with other repair methods. Examples are high strength recovery for the structure and no aerodynamic handicap.

Based on FE results this paper shall demonstrate the dominating stresses and typical stress niveau that could be reached in a military aircraft structure taking into account the orthotropy of laminates, manufacturing quality and adhesive's plasticity.

2. REPAIR TECHNIQUE FOR CFC AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

The basic goal of a CFC repair is to restore or provide sufficient strength of a repaired part, so that the aircraft can fly without limitations. Within the large number of possible CFC repairs methods, the flush scarf repair has become increasingly more interesting. In principle a flush scarf repair is performed by the following steps, Figure 1:

1. Assessment of damage via non-destructive testing methods (ultrasonic, x-ray) and determination of the damage boundaries. If the damage area is relatively large and cannot be tolerated by the structure, a flush scarf bonded repair makes even more sense.
2. Performing a scarf into the original damaged laminate by cutting out or grinding.

3. Bonding a repair patch onto the repair area. The patch shall not be thicker than the original laminate in order to obtain a flush scarf repair.

Although the scarf technique and also the scarf angle of $1/20$ has been widely accepted in the aircraft industry there is no common methodology for the material selection, adhesive, cure cycles etc. For the present FE-investigations it has been assumed that the repair patch material has been cured under autoclave conditions and is similar to the original laminate. This assumption corresponds to the "hard patch repair" method for CFC which has been developed at Deutsche Aerospace [5].

3. MATERIAL DATA FOR HIGH STRENGTH ADHESIVES

The fact that the adhesive is much softer than the materials to be bonded, causes considerable influence of the adherents' geometry and material on the stresses in the glue line [1]. A widely used test method for determination of high strength adhesive data is the thick adherent specimen whose design has been configured to several standards [2]. The specimen can be characterized by relatively thick adherents (e.g. 6 mm) having a short lap length or bondline (e.g. 5 mm). For the validity of the result it is essential that the adhesive fails within the bondline otherwise there will be no confidence in the performance of the glue. The thick adherent specimen yields an almost linear shear stress distribution within the glue line that can easily be calculated by dividing the load by the bonded area [3].

In contrast to the tester's purpose, this specimen also shows peel stresses resulting from the deformation of the adherents, Figure 2. Hence the thick adherent specimen is a good means to determine the shear modulus of the adhesive but its performance in testing pure shear failure is doubtful [4].

A more detailed but expensive and therefore less practical method to get adhesive data is the torsion tube test. The test arrangement allows the determination of pure shear, pure tension and their interaction providing a failure characteristic as shown in Figure 2 for a modified epoxy adhesive. It can be demonstrated by analysis that the maximum peel stress reaches about the same magnitude as the maximum shear stress [2]. Assuming this stress condition the torsion tube test should demonstrate approximately 30% higher shear strength in comparison with that measured by the thick adherent specimen. The conservative strength data resulting from thick adherent specimen tests however is implicitly accounted for by the strength evaluation of bonded joints used in aircraft industry. Only the relationship between the allowable and calculated maximum shear stress must be regarded as peel stresses shall be negligibly low in magnitude.

Material data for the high strength adhesive BSL322A at room temperature resulting from tests with the thick adherent specimen are attached in Figure 3.

4. 2-DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT CALCULATIONS

A 2-dimensional model has been selected to examine the applicability of the chosen FE-method and to determine fundamental influences of adherents' properties on the glue stresses. All calculations have been performed with BSL 322A adhesive data obtained from the thick adherent specimen, Figure 3. The Poisson's ratio has been defined at 0.48. The considered CFC laminate properties correspond to the composite 5245C/T800.

4.1. Stresses within the Bondline

The dominating stresses within a single lap or scarfed joint are shear stresses in the bondline and, to a certain extent, peel stresses normal to it. A microsection of a scarfed bonded joint must confirm the homogeneity of the adherent laminate and the bondline as a result of sophisticated repair experience so that the true conditions can be correlated with the theoretical ones and hence justify a FE analysis.

The advantage of a flush scarf bonded joint compared with a single lap bonded joint, Figure 4, is due to the different stress distribution along the bondline. A typical curve for lap joints is depicted in Figure 5 where high shear and peel stress peaks are noticed at the ends of the adherents. As the bondline stresses increase linearly with the load the maximum shear stress could surmount the allowable one already at low loading levels of the adherents. In the mid-area of the joint all stresses vanish to zero proving that the joint length could be reduced without influence on the stress niveau. The flush scarf bonded joint with isotropic adherents however needs not to sustain such extreme peak stresses in shear and tension. Since the area below the shear stress curve can be interpreted as the strength potential of the joint, the extended performance of a flush scarf bonded joint compared with a single lap bonded joint becomes evident.

For lap joints there is no difference for the stress distribution regarding either isotropic or orthotropic adherents. However, the ply lay-up and stacking sequence of laminates plays an important role for the bonding stresses at scarf joints. In this investigation it was assumed that the oblique cut, i.e. the scarf angle 1:20, through the laminate and thus through a ply is repaired by bonding exactly the same repair ply in lieu of the removed original one. Thus it is clear that there must be a difference in bonding e.g. 0° -plies, representing very stiff adherents, and 90° -plies whose stiffness does not differ too much from that of the glue. The results of a FE-calculation for quasi-isotropic laminate (lay-up: 25/50/25) and a tension type laminate (42/50/8) reflect these stiffness variation in their bondline stress curves, Figure 6.

4.2. Adherent with Truncated Edge

Although being desirable it appears hardly feasible for a manufacturer to produce repair patches with infinite sharp edges. A practical manufacturing standard however must require an allowable edge truncation. This truncated edge plays an important role for the bondline stresses, because a sharp edge with its decreasing stiffness smoothes possible peel stress peaks, a truncated edge however induces a sudden peel stress increase, Figure 7. An edge truncation of only 0.1 mm which corresponds to about the ply thickness of a CFRP laminate presumably will not cause severe problems. A repair patch tolerating a 0.2 mm edge truncation will have lost considerable strength compared with a patch produced with ideal edges. These results recommend to check thoroughly the actual manufacturing quality of a repair in order to obtain an adequate answer from the stress calculation.

5. 3-DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT CALCULATIONS

The goal of the 3-dimensional FE-calculations was to conceive the bonding stress distribution within the total adhesive layer. Especially a load redistribution could be expected when the shear stresses in the adhesive exceed the elastic limit and cause a non-linear response. The model properties chosen for laminate lay-up, thickness and repair patch dimensions, Fi-

gure 8, are representative for military aircraft structures. The following results enabled to decide upon the methodology of future strength checks dealing with flush scarf repairs.

5.1. Isotropic Material

For the linear elastic calculation of a flush scarf repair with aluminium adherents a maximum adhesive shear stress of 28.0 N/mm^2 has been determined, Figure 9, where the adherents being stressed with the elastic limit of the aluminium. In radial direction of the circular repair the typical bonding stress distribution for both shear and peel stresses is obtained. In tangential direction, Figure 10, the magnitude of the stresses decreases from its maximum in load direction (azimuth angle 0°) to zero at 90° . Since a linear increase of adherent stress up to failure load of the aluminium would lead to a linear elastic adhesive shear stress of 35.5 N/mm^2 it makes sense to account for the elastic-plastic behaviour. The reason for that is the excess of 25.5 N/mm^2 standing for the elastic shear stress limit of the adhesive. Figure 11 presents the results of the non-linear calculation referring to a shear stress relief of about 10% (32.1 N/mm^2) at the peaks. The comparison of linear elastic and elasto-plastic calculations demonstrates their similarity i.e. there is no significant redistribution of loads due to the elasto-plastic response.

5.2. Orthotropic Material

Surface laminates being in service at military aircraft used to be designed far below their failure load. This is to meet damage tolerance and repair requirements. These requirements mostly are expressed with the help of a maximum allowable fibre strain which must not be exceeded. Hence a maximum allowable load can be attributed to a laminate ply lay-up so that a stiff laminate must sustain higher loads than it is expected from a less stiff laminate. It is therefore obvious why the repair of a stiff laminate being designed for high loads is a greater challenge than the repair of relative soft laminate.

In Figure 12 the shear stress distribution for the quasi-isotropic laminate (25/50/25, see section 4.1) within the adhesive layer is given, assuming elasto-plastic response of the adhesive. The loading of the adherents was set to the maximum allowable fibre strain for the laminate. The maximum stresses in load direction decrease almost to zero normal to the load direction. Figure 13 expresses the shear stress distribution of the tension type laminate. While the quasi-isotropic laminate causes a shear stress peak at 26.5 N/mm^2 , the tension type CFC reaches 29.5 N/mm^2 . These stress magnitudes are not too far away from the adhesive's elastic limit so that a simple linear elastic calculation can be conceded.

5.3. Comparison of 2D and 3D Calculation

Being tasked with the stress analysis of flush scarf bonded joints, the results of the 3D-calculations suggest to work with a 2-dimensional model rather than accounting for the whole 3-dimensional problem. This method reduces repair analysis tremendously. A direct comparison of 2D and 3D results is given in Figure 14. The maximum shear stresses in load direction of the 3D-FE model are plotted against the values determined with a 2D model. The diagrams only show minor discrepancies between the curves and confirm confidence for future 2-dimensional repair calculations.

6. SUMMARY

The application of flush scarf bonded repairs for aircraft structures made from CFC requires information about the resulting stresses in the glue. In contrast to the bonding stress distributions in isotropic material, where typical shear and peel stress curves are observed, the stresses in scarfed laminate adherents are completely different. They mainly depend on the laminate's ply lay-up and stacking sequence making it impossible to predict magnitude and location of the maximum stresses without a detailed calculation.

Although high strength adhesives show an elasto-plastic load response this investigation could demonstrate that the error is negligible when assuming a linear elastic stress-strain curve. This presupposes the laminates not being higher loaded than the typical ultimate loads for military aircraft structures accounting for damage tolerance and repairability aspects.

The presented results give confidence to the stress engineer who is in charge of proving the strength of the flush scarf repair. It is recommended to perform a 2-dimensional check in the principal stress directions of the repair area.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Comparison of 2D and 3D FEM Calculation

Figure 14